

AGROCHEMICAL AND BIOECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MASSES

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Abstract. *The level of humus and nutrient supply in the genetic layers of grass-gray soils scattered in oases, the distribution, quantity and quality of microorganisms by seasons, the nutrients necessary for their survival, carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and other macro-microelements are listed. The amount of humus in the arable land and subsoil varies widely, the highest values are 1,01-1,45%, total nitrogen 0,087-0,126%, phosphorus – 0,625-0,743%. potassium 1,25-2,0%, the mobile form of Phosphorus, potassium and nitrogen is provided very little. Quantitative indicators of humus reserves in irrigated meadow-gray, gray-meadow, meadow soils of Shurchinsky district in the layer 0-50 cm fluctuated in a short range – 60,90 t / ha, nitrogen – 5,29 t, phosphorus - in the upper. Layer 0-30 cm. 3120 t, potassium 8400 t, the amount of common salts and ions with varying degrees of salinity depending on soil-climatic and economic and living conditions were determined. It was found that a large number of microorganisms corresponds to weak and moderately saline meadow soils irrigated in the past. Microorganisms are abundant in the upper horizons, sufficiently supplied with humus, nitrogen and oxygen, and in the lower ones their number decreases. It was found that the activity of microorganisms seasonally increases in autumn and spring and decreases in summer.*

Keywords: *microorganism, soil biology, soil humus, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and macro-microelements.*

Research object. *The gray-meadow, pale gray soils of "Asl-Dior field" and "shermuhammadbobo" farms of Shorchi district were selected.*

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Areas of irrigated agriculture or oasis in Central Asia are bounded by wide river valleys, intermountain depressions, and mountain ranges that facilitate the flow of river water to the fields. Oasis are located in the belt of gray soils at the foot of the mountains of Central Asia, in the Turanian lowland, a desert zone of Eurasia. The total area of oasis in Central Asia is more than 6 million hectares Litvinovich A.V. Surkhandarya region is located in the southernmost part of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It borders Afghanistan along the Amudarya River in the south, Tajikistan in the north, northeast and east, the Republic of Turkmenistan in the southwest, and the Kashkadarya region in the northwest. The central and southern part of the region is a plain, surrounded by Boisun mountain, Kohitangtog, and Bobotog mountains, which are the continuation of the northern Hisar mountain ranges. In the zone of warm and hot subtropical desert sub-zone, low mountains and sub-mountain slope plains, newly irrigated light-colored gray soils, dry light-colored gray soils, irrigated gray-meadow soils, irrigated desert-meadow settlements, brown-brown soils were selected. Normal growth and development of plants and high-quality harvest largely depend on the agrochemical properties of the soil, including the amount of humus and nutrients. Humus is not only the main source of food for plants, but also a high molecular organic substance that determines the level of soil fertility and regulates their agrophysical, physicochemical and biological properties [1,2]. The biological activity of soil microbiology depends on the type and amount of microorganisms living in the soil. Biochemical

and microbiological studies play an important role in improving soil fertility and crop productivity. It also improves soil fertility and provides nutrients for plants. Important processes such as the transition of elements to an easily digestible state are carried out with the help of microorganisms [4,5,7]. The role of ammonifiers, actinomycetes, fungi and other microorganisms is important in the mineralization of organic matter in the soil and the release of ammonium nitrogen that can be absorbed by plants. Soil fertility is important for rapid growth of microorganisms. In highly fertile and cultured soils, the quantity and quality of microorganisms are high, and the nutrients necessary for their survival include carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and other macro-microelements.

In the conditions of the intensive farming system in recent years, attention is being paid to the increase of arable land, the increase of the cultivated land area, alternating (rotational) planting, improvement of water supply, and the use of organic fertilizers.

The purpose of the study. to determine the level of provision of humus and nutrients and biological activity of meadow-gray, gray meadow, meadow soils.

Research object. Meadow-gray, gray meadow, meadow soils of desert-oase soils were selected.

Research methods. Genetic-geographical and chemical-analytical methods were used in field and office studies. Field soil and office-analytical works were carried out on the basis of methods developed and generally accepted in the institutes of NIIPA and UzNIKh, in particular, on the basis of the "Instructions for conducting soil studies and compiling soil maps for maintaining the State Land Cadastre", "Methods of chemical analysis of soils and plants". Mathematical and statistical analysis of the obtained data was performed using the equation of B.A. Dospekhov. The number of microorganisms was determined by sowing in different nutrient media: ammonifiers - in $\gamma(N-NO_3)$ -meat-peptone agar (GPA) nutrient medium, actinomycetes - in starch-ammonia agar (KAA) nutrient medium, microscopic fungi - in Chapek nutrient medium.

Research results. The amount of humus in the upper plowed and under plowed layers of the irrigated meadow-gray soils of Shorchi district fluctuates widely, the highest values are 1,01-1,45%, total nitrogen 0,087-0,126%, phosphorus-0,625-0,743%, potassium 1,25- is 2,0%. The amount of mobile phosphorus is 7,33-18,93 mg/kg, and potassium is 184-262 mg/kg. These studied desert-meadow soils are very low (0-15) and low (16-30 mg) with mobile nitrogen and phosphorus. /kg), forms a group of soils with very low (0-100), low (100-200) and moderate (201-300 mg/kg) supply of exchangeable potassium. The amount of carbonates (SO₂) in cross-sections is 3,34-7,35%. The ratio of carbon to total nitrogen in humus is 7,8-8,42 in the upper layers (0-55 cm), and 5,8-6,2 in the lower layers (1-table).

1-table

**The main agrochemical parameters of irrigated meadow-gray soils of Shorchi district,
Surkhandarya region**

Depth, cm	Hummus, %	Gross, %			Active, mg/kg		CO ₂ carbonate, %	SO ₄ gypsum, %	pH
		N	P	K	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O			
17-Section. Irrigated meadow - gray soil									
0-30	1,45	0,126	0,743	2,00	18,93	262	7,35	0,403	7,69
30-50	1,01	0,087	0,625	1,25	7,33	184	3,34	0,337	7,64
50-75	0,87	0,073	0,593	1,20	5,33	75	7,04	0,387	7,67

75-100	0,66	0,067	0,593	0,75	5,33	62	6,96	0,420	7,64
100-150	0,59	0,056	0,643	1,10	5,33	66	7,32	0,329	7,67

Gypsum is formed from the solution of seepage water in the soil and the accumulation of salts on the surface of the earth after the evaporation of irrigation water. As a result of the accumulation of Na₂SO₄, MgCO₃, CaCO₃, including exchangeable Sa in the soil solution during this process, small crystals are collected and gypsum is formed. The amount of gypsum is 20% and above.

Gypsum soils have unique water-physical properties and have attracted the attention of soil reclamationists since ancient times due to their high moisture capacity and other properties.

According to the analysis of the soil samples taken from the cuttings placed on the field lands of the base farms, the amount of gypsum in the irrigated meadow-gray soils of the farms of Shorchi district is 0,337-0,403% in the arable layer (30 cm) and (50 cm). The soils of these basic farms are not plastered according to the current classification

(< 10%) is a group of soils (1-table).

According to the analysis of the data, the quantitative indicators of the humus reserve in the irrigated meadow-gray soils of the Shorchi district farm in the cross-section fluctuated in a short interval, and in the upper 0-30 cm layer, 60,90 tons per hectare, nitrogen 5,29 tons, phosphorus 31,20 tons, potassium 84,00 tons (2-table).

2-table

Composition of humus, nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium reserves of irrigated grassland soils of Shorchi district, Surkhandarya region

The name of the soil	Depth, cm	Humus, t/ga	Gross, t/ha		
			N	P	K
1	2	3	4	5	6
Meadow-gray	0-30	60,90	5,29	31,20	84,00
	30-50	28,28	2,43	17,50	35,00
	50-75	30,45	2,55	20,75	42,00
	75-100	23,10	2,34	20,75	26,25
	100-150	44,25	4,20	48,22	82,50

Microelements are great importance in the life of plants. Due to their catalytic effect, they allow plants to use the main nutrients - solar energy, water and macronutrients - nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) more efficiently, which in turn has a positive effect on plant productivity and yield. They are part of enzymes and enzyme systems, without which biochemical processes cannot occur in the plant body. Micronutrients can increase the regenerative capacity of plant tissues, which significantly reduces plant damage from diseases. Many trace elements are active catalysts of biochemical processes in plants. Micronutrients in soil are in various compounds, most of them are insoluble or sparingly soluble forms and only a small part are mobile forms that are assimilated by plants. The mobility of microelements and their availability for plants is greatly influenced by soil acidity, moisture, mechanical composition, amount of organic matter and other conditions. Deficiency of trace elements such as Cu, Zn, Mn, B in the soil primarily reduces the productivity of agricultural plants. The amount of microelements in the soil depends primarily on the amount of their mother rocks and the level of cultivation, soil type, type, etc.

The results of the study show that the microbiological properties of soils change under the influence of salinity, and at the same time, the number of microorganisms changes depending on the season. The diversity of the physico-chemical properties of the studied soils is also reflected in the distribution of soil microorganisms. According to the results of the study, there were significant changes in the number of studied microorganisms depending on the level of salinity.

The data show that the amount of ammonifiers was determined at the highest levels in old irrigated meadow and desert-meadow soils with weak and moderate salinity (Table 3). Here, ammonifiers in weakly saline gray-meadow soils from spring to autumn in the 0-30 cm layer range from $2,1 \times 10^6$ $6,5 \pm 0,2$ to $4,5 \times 10^7$ $7,4 \pm 0,1$ KOE/g, in the 30-60 cm layer 1, 7×10^7 $7,6 \pm 0,2$ to $6,7 \times 10^7$ $7,6 \pm 0,2$ KOE/g, ammonifiers in moderately saline gray-meadow soils from spring to autumn in the 0-30 cm layer $2,2 \times 10^4$ $4,2 \pm 0,2$ to $9,5 \times 10^7$ up to $7,9 \pm 0,1$ KOE/g, in a layer of 30-60 cm from $2,2 \times 10^6$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$ to $4,5 \times 10^7$ $7,4 \pm 0,1$ KOE/g, medium saline irrigated light shade in gray soils, ammonifiers from spring to autumn in the 0-30 cm layer from $2,4 \times 10^4$ $5,1 \pm 0,2$ to $7,3 \times 10^4$ $5,8 \pm 0,1$ KOE/g, in the 30-60 cm layer from $2,5 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,1$ $7,7 \times 10^4$ is up to $8,6 \pm 0,1$ KOE/g.

The minimum amount of ammonifiers in medium saline irrigated gray soils from spring to autumn in the 0-30 cm layer is from $1,1 \times 10^3$ $4,1 \pm 0,1$ to $9,5 \times 10^7$ $7,9 \pm 0,1$ KOE/g, in the 30-60 cm layer 1, 4×10^8 to $9,5 \times 10^7$ was $7,9 \pm 0,1$ KOE/gr, this distribution in these soils depends on the degree of salinity and light mechanical composition. As we know, the life activity of microorganisms depends on the soil. The amount of ammonifying bacteria decreases according to the laws of genetic layers.

The more favorable the conditions for microorganisms in the soil, the more rapid the development and activity. Accordingly, During the research, it was found that the state of cultivation of the studied soils and the duration of the irrigation period have a significant effect on the soil microflora. According to this, it was found that the old irrigated medium-cultivated meadow soils are provided with a higher amount of ammonifiers than the medium-cultivated meadow-sage soils.

One of the useful properties of actinomycetes is the role of bacteria, actinomycetes and fungi in the conversion of nitrogen from organic substances to mineral mineral nitrogen [1] According to the study of the quantity of actinomycetes, actinomycetes were found in the highest values in weak and medium salinity old irrigated meadow and medium salinity desert-meadow soils (3-.table). Actinomycetes were not found in some sections in the lower layers of moderately saline meadow soils. Actinomycetes in weakly saline gray-meadow soils from spring to autumn in the 0-30 cm layer from $1,5 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,1$ to $7,5 \times 10^3$ $3,7 \pm 0,3$ KOE/g, in the 30-60 cm layer $1,5 \times 10^6$ 8, From $1 \pm 0,1$ to $6,7 \times 10^7$ $7,6 \pm 0,2$ KOE/g, in the upper layer of moderately saline gray-meadow soils from $1,4 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$ to $7,5 \times 10^4$ $4,7 \pm 0,2$ up to KOE/gr, in the 30-60 cm layer from $2,2 \times 10^6$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$ to $7,5 \times 10^3$ $3,7 \pm 0,3$ KOE/gr and not determined in some sections, the lowest amount is $1,1 \times 10^5$ in light gray soils $6,1 \pm 0,2$ to $7,5 \times 10^4$ $4,7 \pm 0,2$ KOE/g, in a layer of 30-60 cm $1,2 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$ to $6,7 \times 10^7$ $7,6 \pm 0,1$ KOE/ appeared gr.

According to the obtained results, oligonitrophils were found at the highest levels in weak and medium salinity old irrigated meadow and medium salinity meadow soils during the study. Oligonitrophils were not detected during the research in the 0-30 cm layer in the autumn season in moderately saline meadow soils and in the 30-60 cm layer in the summer and autumn seasons in the meadow soils (3-table). Oligonitrophils in weakly saline gray-meadow soils in the upper layer from $1,2 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$ to $4,3 \times 10^5$ $5,4 \pm 0,2$ KOE/g, in the 30-60 cm layer $3,2 \times 10^6$ $6,3 \pm 0,2$

from $6,7 \times 10^7$ to $7,6 \pm 0,2$ KOE/gr, in the arable layer of light gray soils from $1,1 \times 10^3$ $3,1 \pm 0,1$ to $6,7 \times 10^7$ $7,6 \pm 0,1$ KOE/gr in autumn in some sections was not determined in the 30-60 cm layer, from $1,5 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,1$ to $9,5 \times 10^7$ $7,9 \pm 0,1$ KOE/g, and in some sections it was not detected in the summer and autumn seasons. The lowest amount of oligonitrophils in moderately saline gray-meadow soils is from $1,1 \times 10^3$ $3,1 \pm 0,1$ to $5,2 \times 10^5$ $5,5 \pm 0,2$ KOE/g in some sections, not detected in autumn, in the 30-60 cm layer $1,5 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,1$ to $4,8 \times 10^6$ was found to be $7,4 \pm 0,2$ KOE/gr.

Fungi belong to the plant world, like microorganisms and bacteria. According to its structure, it is more complex than bacteria and differs from higher plants due to the absence of chlorophyll granules. It is a frost-resistant microorganism, and it was observed that it was not detected at all in the regions where we conducted research, that is, in moderately saline meadow-salvaceous soils, in some sections in the 0-30 cm layer in summer and autumn, and in some sections in the 30-60 cm layer in the grassland soils, of course, this provision of sufficient moisture is positive for various fungi.

Becomes invisible with the effect. Fungi in weakly saline gray-meadow soils in the 0-30 cm layer $1,2 \times 10^8$ $4,4 \pm 0,2$ to $4,7 \times 10^7$ $6,6 \pm 0,2$ 30-60 cm $3,7 \times 10^6$ $6,3 \pm 0,2$ to $7,5 \times 10^6$ up to $6,7 \pm 0,3$ KOE/g, in medium -saline gray-meadow soils in the 0-30 cm layer from $4,3 \times 10^6$ $6,4 \pm 0,2$ to $9,0 \times 10^6$ $6,9 \pm 0,2$ was not determined in some sections, 30-60 cm $1,5 \times 10^4$ $4,1 \pm 0,2$ to $6,0 \times 10^7$ $7,6 \pm 0,1$ KOE/g, on light gray soils $1,4 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$ to $9,5 \times 10^7$ $7,$ up to $9 \pm 0,1$, in the lower layers from $1,2 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$ to $7,5 \times 10^7$ $6,9 \pm 0,1$ KOE/gr, in some sections it was not determined in summer and autumn seasons (3-table).

3-table

The dynamics of changes in the amount of microorganisms in the soils of the Southern region, Surkhandarya region, according to the seasons (KOE/gr)

Cross section and fold depth, cm	ammonifiers			actinomycetes			oligonitrophils			fungi		
	spring	summer	autumn									
Shorchi district Asl-Dior field massif gray-meadow soil												
0-30	$2,2 \times 10^6$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$	$4,5 \times 10^7$ $7,4 \pm 0,1$	$4,3 \times 10^5$ $5,4 \pm 0,2$	$7,0 \times 10^6$ $5,3 \pm 0,2$	$2,2 \times 10^6$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$	$4,5 \times 10^7$ $7,4 \pm 0,1$	$4,3 \times 10^5$ $5,4 \pm 0,2$	$2,6 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$	$1,5 \times 10^6$ $7,1 \pm 0,1$	$2,2 \times 10^6$ $7,1 \pm 0,1$	$4,0 \times 10^7$ $7,4 \pm 0,2$	$4,7 \times 10^7$ $6,6 \pm 0,2$
30-60	$5,7 \times 10^6$ $6,5 \pm 0,2$	$1,5 \times 10^6$ $8,1 \pm 0,1$	$3,7 \times 10^6$ $6,3 \pm 0,2$	$3,4 \times 10^6$ $6,3 \pm 0,2$	$4,5 \times 10^6$ $6,4 \pm 0,2$	$1,5 \times 10^6$ $8,1 \pm 0,1$	$3,2 \times 10^6$ $6,3 \pm 0,2$	$6,0 \times 10^6$ $8,6 \pm 0,1$	$5,2 \times 10^7$ $7,5 \pm 0,1$	$7,5 \times 10^6$ $6,7 \pm 0,3$	$3,7 \times 10^6$ $6,3 \pm 0,2$	$5,7 \times 10^6$ $6,5 \pm 0,2$
0-30	$4,4 \times 10^6$ $6,4 \pm 0,2$	$2,1 \times 10^6$ $6,5 \pm 0,2$	$2,2 \times 10^6$ $6,3 \pm 0,2$	$7,5 \times 10^3$ $3,7 \pm 0,2$	$1,5 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$	$3,7 \times 10^7$ $7,3 \pm 0,2$	$1,2 \times 10^8$ $8,1 \pm 0,2$	$1,4 \times 10^7$ $6,3 \pm 0,2$	$2,2 \times 10^8$ $5,1 \pm 0,2$	$1,2 \times 10^8$ $4,4 \pm 0,2$	$1,6 \times 10^8$ $7,1 \pm 0,2$	$1,2 \times 10^8$ $5,1 \pm 0,2$

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	0,2	0,2	6,2 ±0, 2	0,3	0,1	0,1	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	2
30-60	6,7x 10 ⁷ 7,6± 0,2	1,7x 10 ⁷ 7,6± 0,2	6,7 x10 ⁷ 7,6 ±0, 2	6,7x 10 ⁷ 7,6± 0,2	6,7x1 0 ⁷ 7,6±0, 2							
"Shermuhammad Bobo" massif, Shorchi district, grassy soil												
0-30	4,3x 10 ⁶ 6,4± 0,2	3,0x 10 ⁶ 6,9± 0,2	5,3 x10 ⁶ 6,5 ±0, 2	2,2x 10 ⁵ 5,2± 0,2	7,5x 10 ⁴ 4,7± 0,2	1,5x 10 ⁵ 5,1± 0,2	2,2x 10 ⁵ 5,2± 0,2	1,5x 10 ⁴ 4,1± 0,2	1,1x 10 ³ 3,1± 0,1	4,3x 10 ⁶ 6,4± 0,2	9,0x 10 ⁶ 6,9± 0,2	5,3x1 0 ⁶ 6,5±0, 2
30-60	1,4x 10 ⁸ 7,1± 0,2	4,5x 10 ⁷ 7,4± 0,1	6,7 x10 ⁷ 7,6 ±0, 2	2,2x 10 ⁴ 4,2± 0,2	5,2x 10 ⁵ 5,5± 0,2	1,5x 10 ⁴ 4,1± 0,2	3,0x 10 ⁵ 5,3± 0,1	1,5x 10 ⁴ 4,1± 0,2	2,2x 10 ⁵ 5,2± 0,2	1,2x 10 ⁸ 8,1± 0,2	4,5x 10 ⁷ 7,4± 0,1	6,7x1 0 ⁷ 7,6±0, 2
0-30	2,5x 10 ² 3,4± 0,1	1,1x 10 ³ 4,1± 0,1	2,7 x10 ³ 3,6 ±0, 2	1,5x 10 ³ 4,2± 0,2	1,1x 10 ⁵ 6,1± 0,2	6,2x 10 ⁴ 6,5± 0,1	1,6x 10 ⁴ 6,1± 0,2	1,9x 10 ³ 5,1± 0,1	1,5x 10 ⁴ 7,1± 0,1	2,2x 10 ⁴ 6,1± 0,2	5,5x 10 ³ 4,4± 0,1	6,7x1 0 ⁵ 5,6±0, 2
30-60	2,2x 10 ⁴ 4,2± 0,2	6,7x 10 ⁷ 7,6± 0,1	9,5 x10 ⁷ 7,9 ±0, 1	1,4x 10 ⁸ 8,1± 0,2	2,2x 10 ⁴ 4,2± 0,2	6,7x 10 ⁷ 7,6± 0,1	9,5x 10 ⁷ 7,9± 0,1	7,2x 10 ⁵ 6,7± 0,2	1,5x 10 ⁸ 6,1± 0,1	6,7x 10 ⁷ 8,6± 0,1	7,5x 10 ⁷ 6,9± 0,1	1,7x1 0 ⁵ 7,1±0, 2
0-30	6,7x 10 ⁷ 7,6± 0,1	9,5x 10 ⁷ 7,9± 0,1	1,4 x10 ⁸ 8,1 ±0, 2	1,5x 10 ⁴ 4,1± 0,2	2,2x 10 ⁵ 5,2± 0,2	1,2x 10 ⁸ 8,1± 0,2	4,5x 10 ⁷ 7,4± 0,1	6,7x 10 ⁷ 7,6± 0,2	2,2x 10 ⁴ 4,2± 0,2	6,7x 10 ⁷ 7,6± 0,1	9,5x 10 ⁷ 7,9± 0,1	1,4x1 0 ⁸ 8,1±0, 2
30-60	5,2x 10 ⁵ 3,5± 0,2	1,5x 10 ⁴ 4,1± 0,2	3,0 x10 ³ 3,3	1,5x 10 ⁸ 8,1± 0,2	3,7x 10 ⁷ 7,3± 0,1	6,7x 10 ⁷ 7,6± 0,2	7,5x 10 ⁴ 4,7± 0,3	- -	- -	6,0x 10 ⁵ 5,6± 0,3	- -	- -

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A large amount of microorganisms corresponds to old irrigated weak and moderately saline meadow soils. Microorganisms are abundant in the upper horizons, sufficiently supplied with humus, nitrogen and oxygen, and their number decreases in the lower horizons.

Seasonal dynamics of biological processes are great importance in the soils of the region. Unfavorable climatic conditions of the studied gray oasis regions, i.e. high summer temperature, low relative humidity, rapid rise of moisture from the soil, low organic matter content, lead to a decrease in the microbiological activity of the soil in the area. Therefore, the intensive activity of microorganisms corresponds to the spring period, their activity decreases in summer, and their number increases significantly by autumn.

In short, according to the amount of nutrients - mobile nitrogen and phosphorus, meadow-gray soils are very low and low, and according to the amount of exchangeable potassium, they form a group of soils that are very low and low. 60,90 tons per hectare, 5,29 tons of nitrogen, 31,20 tons of phosphorus, 84,00 tons of potassium per hectare in the cm layer, and the lowest amount in the old irrigated weak and moderately saline gray-meadow and the old irrigated moderately saline pale gray soils it became known.

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